

University
of Basel

CURAC

Deutsche Gesellschaft für Computer-
und Roboterassistierte Chirurgie e. V.

22. Jahrestagung
der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Computer-
und Roboterassistierte Chirurgie (CURAC)
24. - 26. August 2023, Universität Basel
"Medical Robotics Week"

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CURAC 2023 BASEL

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CURAC 2023 BASEL

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Roboterassistierte Chirurgie e.V.

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VORSTAND

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Grussworte der Tagungspräsidenten

Sehr geehrte Damen und Herren,
liebe Kolleginnen und Kollegen,
liebe CURAC-Mitglieder,

die Deutsche Gesellschaft für Computer- und Roboterassistierte Chirurgie e.V. möchte Sie dieses Jahr herzlich in Basel vom 24.08. – 26.08.2023 begrüßen.

Dieses Jahr steht unter dem Motto „Medical Robotics Week“, wo wir rund um das Programm der CURAC Konferenz selbst auch noch Workshops und Funding Events anbieten.

Zunächst möchten wir uns aber auch beim Organisationsteam der letzten CURAC in Karlsruhe rund um Frau Prof. Franziska Mathis-Ullrich bedanken für die gelungene Tagung im Herbst 2022!

Wir freuen uns über Einreichungen von full Papers oder extended Abstracts über alle Themen, die in den Bereich von Computer- und Roboterassistierter Chirurgie fallen sowie verwandte Themengebiete von medizinischer Bildverarbeitung, Instrumenten Registrierung, Navigation, Chirurgierobotik, chirurgische Tools, neue Behandlungsformen, Automatisierung in Spitälern, Verwendung von Machine Learning und KI rund um OPs, Diagnose und Workflow im Spital, Verwendung von virtueller/augmented Reality im Spital.

Dieses Jahr möchten wir Ihnen Basel und seine Forschung rund um Computer- und Roboterassistierte Chirurgie vorstellen. Basel ist nicht um sonst eine der innovativsten Städte der Welt, die aber auch kulturell und ihrer Lage am Rhein und am Dreiländereck zwischen Deutschland, Frankreich und der Schweiz viel zu bieten hat.

Dieses Jahr dürfen wir auch auf die Unterstützung des Schweizer Nationalfonds (SNSF) zählen, der uns erlaubt viele renommierte lokale aber auch internationale Keynote Redner einzuladen. Weiters freuen wir uns auf die tatkräftige Unterstützung auch von Sponsoren aus der Industrie.

Für die späte Einladung dieses Jahr möchten wir uns entschuldigen und uns für Ihre Geduld bedanken. Hoffen dafür, dass die späte Beitragsdeadline allen entgegenkommt.

Das CURAC-Organisationsteam und ich freuen uns, Sie alle in Basel am BIOZENTRUM der Universität Basel begrüßen zu dürfen. Wir freuen uns auf das Wiedersehen und den Austausch!

Herzliche Grüße aus Allschwil,

Prof. Dr. Georg Rauter
(Tagungspräsident)

Prof. Dr. med. Beat Müller
(Co-Organisator)

Tagungspräsident

Georg Rauter

Vorsitzende des Programm Komitees

Georg Rauter

Beat Müller

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Medical Robotics Week 2023 – Workshop Days

Tuesday, 22. Aug. 2023 - Workshop Day 1		
Workshop 1 (Day1) Practical industry workshop for TwinCat3 (Beckhoff AG) and Matlab/Simulink (Mathworks) <i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
8:30	9:00	Registration and coffee
9:00	9:10	Welcome Georg Rauter
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
9:10	9:30	Introduction to real-time systems Tobias Bachmann
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
9:30	9:50	Reading schematics of control cabinets Georg Rauter
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
9:50	10:10	Software installation and programming platform Georg Rauter
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
10:10	10:40	First steps in Matlab/Simulink Vasco Lenzi
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
10:40	11:00	Coffee break
11:00	12:40	My first Matlab/Simulink program in TwinCat3 Georg Rauter
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
12:40	14:00	Lunch break
14:00	15:40	Safety in TwinCAT 3 Georg Rauter
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>		
15:40	16:00	Coffee break
16:00	17:40	Implementing a servo motor in Matlab/Simulink for TwinCat3 Georg Rauter
17:40		Voluntary GetTogether (Restaurant zum Tell, Spalenvorstadt 38, 4051 Basel)

Wednesday, 23. Aug. 2023 - Workshop Day 2					
Workshop 1 (Day 2) Practical industry workshop for TwinCat3 (Beckhoff AG) and Matlab/Simulink (Mathworks) <i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			Workshop 3 (Morning) Fiber-based systems for robotics and medical applications <i>Seminar room 02.073</i>		
			Workshop 2 (Afternoon) Young Surgineers <i>Seminar room U1.197</i>		
9:00	10:40	Matlab/Simulink state flow programming Vasco Lenzi	9:00	10:40	Introduction to optics, fibers, lasers, and applications (background of potential applications in robotics and medicine)
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			<i>Seminar room 02.073</i>		
10:40 - 11:00 Coffee break					
11:00	12:40	Implementation of basic controllers in Matlab/Simulink for control of a servo motor in TwinCAT3 & Intro to User Interface (PLC & HMI) Georg Rauter	11:00	11:40	Optical coherence tomography, available and potential applications
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			<i>Seminar room 02.073</i>		
			11:40	12:40	Fiber-based shape sensing, available and potential applications
			<i>Seminar room 02.073</i>		
12:40 - 14:00 Lunch break					
14:00	15:40	TwinCat3 Vision Tobias Bachmann	13:00	14:30	Young Surgineers Session
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			<i>Seminar room U1.197</i>		
15:40 - 16:10 Coffee break					
16:10	17:35	Demonstration of visual servoing using Matlab/Simulink in TwinCAT3 Vision Nicolas Gerig	15:00	16:45	Young Surgineers Session
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			<i>Seminar room U1.197</i>		
				15:45	17:00
17:35	17:40	Wrap up and Conclusions Georg Rauter	17:00	18:00	Young Surgineers Session
<i>Seminar room 01.006</i>			<i>Seminar room U1.197</i>		
			18:30	20:00	Vorstandssitzung Only CURAC board
			<i>Seminar room U1.197</i>		
20:30	Voluntary GetTogether (Restaurant Zum Isaak, Münsterplatz 16, Basel)				

Medical Robotics Week 2023 – CURAC Days

Thursday, 24. Aug. 2023 - CURAC Day 1	
CURAC Day 1 <i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
Innovation Booster Robotics event (Afternoon) <i>Auditorium U1.101</i>	
7:30 8:30	Präsidiumssitzung Only CURAC steering committee
<i>Seminar room U1.197</i>	
8:30 9:00	Registration and coffee
<i>Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2</i>	
9:00 9:05	Welcome from CURAC President Thomas Klenzner (Universitätsklinikum Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany)
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
9:05 9:20	Welcome from General Chair MRW2023 & CURAC2023 Georg Rauter (University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland)
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
9:20 9:25	Welcome from Medical Chair CURAC 2023 Beat Müller (Clarunis - Universitäres Bauchzentrum, Basel, Switzerland)
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
9:25 9:30	Welcome Lukas Engelberger (President of the Gesundheitsdirektorenkonferenz)
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
9:30 10:15	KeyNote 1 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> Aude Billard (EPFL, Switzerland) «Robotic assistance for 4-handed manipulation with application to Laparoscopic Surgery»
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
10:15 10:30	Industry Pitches Guest
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
10:30 11:00	Coffee break and industry exhibition
<i>Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2</i>	
11:00 12:00	Session 1: Robotics and Navigation <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> 4 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
11:00 – 11:15	“A Novel End Effector for Telemanipulated Suturing in Robot-Assisted Laparoscopy” <u>Kirst, Alexander</u> ; Hellings-Kuß, Anja; Hagmann, Katharina; Dyck, Michael; Schlenk, Christopher; Klodmann, Julian
11:15 – 11:30	“Nullspace Control for Automatic Ultrasound Gel Supply” <u>Osburg, Jonas</u> ; Ernst, Floris
11:30 – 11:45	“Robot-assisted Neuroendoscopy: Surgeon’s Third Hand – a Proof of Concept Study” <u>Karnam, Murali</u> ; Rychen, Jonathan; Guzman, Raphael; Cattin, Philippe; Rauter, Georg; Gerig, Nicolas
11:45 – 12:00	“Feasibility and accuracy of CARLO® guided optic canal unroofing” <u>Schicker, Martina</u> ; Ha, Thanh Tu; Luder, Yann; Morawska, Marta; Röthlisberger, Michel
12:00 12:30	Poster Session 1: Short presentation to posters <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> 10x 3min Talk
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	
12:00 – 12:03	Poster 1: “Spatially-constrained Keypoint Matching for Efficient Statistical Shape Modelling” <u>Harkämper, Lena</u> ; Großbröhmer, Christoph; <u>Himstedt, Marian</u>
12:03 – 12:06	Poster 2: “Innovating Instrument Handover Techniques for Robotic Scrub Nurses” <u>Scheppach, Carl</u> ; Wagner, Lars; Spinner, Caroline; Jell, Alissa; Wilhelm, Dirk

12:06 – 12:09	Poster 3: “Feasibility and accuracy of CARLO© guided extradural anterior clinoidectomy” <u>Ha, Thanh Tu</u> ; Schicker, Martina; Cordier, Dominik; Luder, Yann; Morawska, Marta; Röthlisberger, Michel
12:09 – 12:12	Poster 4: “Optical coherence tomography-guided laser osteotomy: toward improvement of ablation efficiency” <u>Hamidi, Arsham</u> ; Cattin, Philippe C.; Canbaz, Ferda
12:12 – 12:15	Poster 5: “Feet-Driven 4-Arm Manipulation: A Novel Approach for Solo Laparoscopic Anastomosis” <u>Gholami, Soheil</u> ; <u>Munier, Louis</u> ; <u>Cabasse, Cecile</u> ; Bouri, Mohamed; Billard, Aude
12:15 – 12:18	Poster 6: “Deep Learning-based Artificial Intelligence in Audio based Analysis of Swallowing using Cervical Auscultation” Salloum, Hazem; <u>Graf, Simone</u> ; Schilling, Berit; Richter, Lena; Jeleff-Wölfler, Olivia; Feussner, Hubertus; Ostler, Daniel; Wilhelm, Dirk; Fuchtmann, Jonas
12:18 – 12:21	Poster 7: “Model to Simulate Brain Biopsies Using a Navigated Robotic Guiding System and a Bone Cutting Laser” <u>Ha, Thanh Tu</u> ; <u>Luder, Yann</u> ; Röthlisberger, Michel; Schicker, Martina; Morawska, Marta; Cordier, Dominik
12:21 – 12:24	Poster 8: “Feature Description using Autoencoders for Fast 3D Ultrasound Tracking” <u>Wulff, Daniel</u> ; Ernst, Floris
12:24 – 12:27	Poster 9: “Gamified Virtual Reality Training for Visuospatial Ability in Neuroradiology” <u>Allgaier, Maren</u> ; Härtel, Tim Jered; Zubel, Seraphine; Thormann, Maximilian; Behme, Daniel; Preim, Bernhard; Saalfeld, Sylvia
12:27 – 12:30	Poster 10: “Target Tracking in 4D Ultrasound using Localization Networks” <u>Krause, Cassandra</u> ; <u>Wulff, Daniel</u> ; Ernst, Floris
12:30 14:00	Lunch break and industry exhibition
Hall UTQ1 & UTQ2	

14:00	14:45	KeyNote 2 Franziska Mathis-Ullrich (FAU, Erlangen, Germany) «Towards Natural Co-Operation with Surgical Robotics» <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>	14:00	15:45	Innovation Booster Robotics event
Auditorium U1.131			Auditorium U1.101		
14:45	15:45	Session 2: Surgical Assistance Systems & Image Processing, Quantification and Visualization (12min Talk + 3min Q&A) <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>			
Auditorium U1.131					
	14:45 – 15:00	“Corrective Cold Ablation Robot-Guided Laser Osteotomies in Wrist Surgery” <u>Hofer, Maximilian</u> ; Coppo, Enrico; Morawska, Marta; Müller-Gerbl, Magdalena; Thieringer, Florian M.; Honigmann, Philipp			
	15:00 – 15:15	“Extended upper GI functional assessment in dysphagia by synchronized intraesophageal ultrasound and fluoroscopy” <u>Jell, Alissa</u> ; Geiger, Alexander; Bernhard, Lukas; Gassert, Florian; Feußner, Hubertus			
15:15	16:15	Coffee break and industry exhibition			
Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2					

16:15	17:00	KeyNote 3 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> Ryo Takeda (Hokkaido University, Sapporo, Japan) «The Importance of Numerical Estimation and Experimental Verification of Clinical Applicable Biomechanical Research: From Blood Vessels to Ligament Tissues»	16:15	18:00	Innovation Booster Robotics event
Auditorium U1.131			Auditorium U1.101		
17:00	18:00	CTAC Session <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> 4 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)			
Auditorium U1.131					
17:00 – 17:15		“From Black-Box to Wisdom-oriented Healthcare: A Glance into Model-Guided Medicine!” <u>Mario Cypko</u>			
17:15 – 17:30		“Implants with actors and sensors to improve the healing of bone fractures - an update from the Smart Implants project” <u>Bergita Ganse</u>			
17:30 – 17:45		“Improving surgical skill assessment using robotics” <u>Joël Lanvanchy</u>			
17:45 – 18:00		“Cognitive Surgical Robots for Laparoscopic Surgery” <u>Martin Wagner</u>			
18:00	21:00	Get together Biozentrum, University of Basel, Spitalstrasse 41, 4056 Basel			
Main entrance, Biozentrum, University of Basel					

Friday, 25. Aug. 2023 - CURAC Day 2	
CURAC Day 2 and members assembly <i>Auditorium U1.131</i>	Lunch symposium <i>Auditorium U1.131</i>
8:00 8:30	Registration and coffee <i>Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2</i>
8:30 9:15	KeyNote 4 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> Jaydev Prataprai Desai (Georgia Tech, Atlanta, USA) «Robotic Transcatheter Delivery of Mitral Valve Implant»
9:15 10:15	Session 3: “Best Paper Session” <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> 4 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)
9:15 – 9:30	“Communication System Using Natural Language for Robotic Laparoscope Guidance” <u>Pan, Yan</u> ; Bernhard, Lukas; Fan, Cheng; Beckendorf, Lukas; Wilhelm, Dirk; Feußner, Hubertus; Groh, Georg
9:30 – 9:45	“A Laryngoscope with Shape Memory Actuation” <u>Fischer, Nikola</u> ; Ho, Patty; Marzi, Christian; Schuler, Patrick; Mathis-Ullrich, Franziska
9:45 – 10:00	“Characterization of Dynamic Gripping Force Feedback for Robot-Assisted Surgery” <u>Schäfer, Max B.</u> ; Riepe, Sarah; Parenzan, Matthias; Bauer, Christian J. E.; Hotz, Jonas; Meiringer, Johannes G.; Weiland, Sophie; Pott, Peter P.
10:00 – 10:15	“In situ minimally invasive 3D printing for bone and cartilage regeneration - a scoping review” <u>Mainitz, Michaela*</u> ; Tomooka, Yukiko*; Eugster, Manuela; Gerig, Nicolas; Sharma, Neha; Thieringer, Florian M.; Rauter, Georg
10:15 10:25	Poster Session 2: Short presentation to posters <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> 5 x 3min Talk
10:15 – 10:18	Poster 11: “Speech Recognition for the Sterile Interaction with Information Systems in the Surgical Area” <u>Schrüfer, Katrin</u> ; Noortwijk, Pascal; <u>Junger, Denise</u> ; Burgert, Oliver
10:18 – 10:21	Poster 12: “6G in Clinical Applications: Integrating New Network Approaches in Healthcare” <u>Kolb, Sven</u> ; <u>Jurosch, Franziska</u> ; Kröger, Nicolai; Mehmeti, Fidan; Bernhard, Lukas; Fuchtmann, Jonas; Speidel, Stefanie; Kellerer, Wolfgang; Wilhelm, Dirk
10:21 – 10:24	Poster 13: “Center for Intelligent Optics” <u>Canbaz, Ferda</u>
10:25 10:45	Coffee break and industry exhibition
10:45 11:30	KeyNote 5 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> Nassir Navab (TU Munich, Munich, Germany) «The Path from Intelligence Amplification to Artificial Intelligence in Computer Assisted Interventions»
11:30 12:15	Guided poster round <i>Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2</i> All poster presenters present at their poster

12:15	14:00	Lunch break and industry exhibition	12:45	14:00	Lunch symposium Main sponsor: <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i> Jean-Marc Collet (Stäubli AG, Switzerland) «Robots at the heart of clinical interventions»
Hall U1Q1 & U1Q2			Auditorium U1.131.		
14:00	14:45	KeyNote 6 Matthias Harders (Universität Innsbruck, Austria) «Recent Developments in Surgical Simulation»	<i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>		
Auditorium U1.131					
14:45	15:45	Session 4: Intelligent OR Technique & Machine Learning 4 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)	<i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>		
Auditorium U1.131					
14:45 – 15:00	“Towards examiner-independent reproducible abdominal ultrasound examinations” Baader, Tobias; Bach, Thanh Nam; Yavuz, Sümeyra; Brand, Lukas Klaus; Güler, Beyda; Grupp, Peter; Malek, Nisar Peter; Hoffmann, Tatjana; Pauluschke-Fröhlich, Jan; Fröhlich, Eckhart; <u>Burgert Oliver</u>				
15:00 – 15:15	“Dynamic Torque Limitation vs Static Torque Limitation for Bone Screws in Pig Bone” <u>Wilkie, Jack</u> ; Richard, Jordan; Joshi, Aditya; McFarlane, Zoe; Staiger, Mark; Rauter, Georg; Möller, Knut				
15:15 – 15:30	“Contactless Energy Supply for Medical Drill with integrated Temperature Sensor” <u>Knott, Anna-Lena</u> ; Sanders, Mark; Prinzen, Tom; Klenzner, Thomas; Schipper, Jörg; Kristin, Julia; Schmitt, Robert H.				
15:30 – 15:45	“Adaptive Contrast Enhancement for Digital Radiographic Images using Image-to-Image Translation” <u>Popp, Ann-Kathrin</u> ; Schumacher, Mona; Himstedt, Marian				
15:45	16:15	Organizer KeyNote Beat Müller (Clarunis - Universitäres Bauchzentrum, Basel, Switzerland) «Robotic surgical oncology»	<i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>		
Auditorium U1.131					
16:15	16:30	Coffee break and industry exhibition			
16:30	17:15	KeyNote 7 Tobias Keck (Universitätsklinikum Schleswig Holstein, Lübeck, Germany) «Potential von Robotik und AI in der klinischen Chirurgie»	<i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>		
Auditorium U1.131					
17:15	18:15	Members Assembly CURAC Only CURAC members	17:15	18:15	Lab Tour: 3D Printlab at the point of care Florian Thieringer (Universtitätsspital Basel - Mund-, Kiefer- und Gesichtschirurgie, Basel, Switzerland)
Auditorium U1.131			3D-Printlab University Hospital Basel		
18:15	18:45	Lab Tour: 3D Printlab at the point of care Florian Thieringer (Universtitätsspital Basel - Mund-, Kiefer- und Gesichtschirurgie, Basel, Switzerland)			
3D-Printlab University Hospital Basel					
19:00	23:00	Conference Dinner, Best Paper & Best Poster Award Ceremony Hotel Krafft, Rheingasse 12, 4058 Basel			
Hotel Krafft, Basel					

Saturday, 26. Aug. 2023 - CURAC Day 3		
8:00	8:30	Registration and coffee
8:30	9:15	KeyNote 8 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>
Auditorium U1.131		Daniel Murariu (Univ. of Pittsburgh Med. School., PA, USA) «Robotics in Plastic Surgery»
9:15	10:45	Session 5: Modeling and Simulation <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>
Auditorium U1.131		6 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)
9:15 – 9:30	“Morphologic and hemodynamic analysis of intracranial mirror aneurysms” <u>Spitz, Lena</u> ; Schmidt, Jessica; Korte, Jana; Berg, Philipp; Behme, Daniel; Neyazi, Belal; Preim, Bernard; Saalfeld, Sylvia	
9:30 – 9:45	“Testing of Bone-Implant Systems equipped with a Fracture Monitor regarding Interfragmentary Movement – A Simulation-Based Workflow” <u>Wickert, Kerstin</u> ; Roland, Michael; Andres, Annchristin; Orth, Marcel; Müller, Max; Ganse, Bergita; Pohlemann, Tim; Diebels, Stefan	
9:45 – 10:00	“Hyper-redundant endoscopic manipulator position compensation under external load” <u>Giacoppo, Giuliano A.</u> ; Schulze, Eric; Pott, Peter P.	
10:00 – 10:15	“Interactive Surgical Liver Phantom for Cholecystectomy Training” <u>Schüßler, Alexander</u> ; Younis, Rayan; Paik, Jamie; Wagner, Martin; Mathis-Ullrich, Franziska; Kunz, Christian	
10:15 – 10:30	“A Calibration Approach for Elasticity Estimation with Medical Tools” <u>Grube, Sarah</u> ; Neidhardt, Maximilian; Hermann, Anna-Katarina; Sprenger, Johanna; Abdolazizi, Kian; Latus, Sarah; Cyron, Christian J.; Schläfer, Alexander	
10:30 – 10:45	“Symmetric single-input eccentric tube robot (ETR) for manual use” <u>Mayer, Juliane</u> ; Dumancic, Marcel; Pott, Peter P.	
10:45	11:15	Coffee break and industry exhibition
11:15	12:00	KeyNote 9 <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>
Auditorium U1.131		Qiu Shao (Maastricht University Medical Center) «The Journey of creating the first microsurgical dedicated robot. When engineers meet plastic surgeons»
12:00	13:00	Session 6: Image Processing, Quantification and Visualizatio <i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>
Auditorium U1.131		4 x (12min Talk + 3min Q&A)
12:00 – 12:15	“Pose Measurement of the EndoWrist Round Tip Scissor Instrument with Optical Coherence Tomography” <u>Schöne, Sandra</u> ; Pol, Nirmal; Kahrs, Lueder A.	
12:15 – 12:30	“Correlating Cerebral Aneurysm Size Measurements Based On Virtual Reality Versus Standard 2D DSA Measurements; A Randomized Comparative Study” <u>Saemann, Attil</u> ; de Wilde, Daniel; Rychen, Jonathan; Röthlisberger, Michel; Zelechowski, Marek; Faludi, Balazs; Cattin, Philippe C.	
12:30 – 12:45	“VR-based body tracking to stimulate musculoskeletal training” Neidhardt, Maximilian; Gerlach, Stefan; Schmidt, Felix N.; Fiedler, Imke A. K.; <u>Grube, Sarah</u> ; Busse, Björn; Schlaefer, Alexander	
12:45 – 13:00	“Intraoperative navigated ultrasound in posterior fossa surgery” <u>Bopp, Miriam</u> ; Saß, Benjamin; Pojskic, Mirza; Grote, Alexander; Nimsky, Christopher	
13:00	13:30	Lunch break

13:30	14:15	KeyNote 10	<i>Chairs: 1, 2</i>
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>		Med Amine Laribi (CNRS-Université de Poitiers-ISAE ENSMA, France) «Robot Design: Application to Medical Robotics»	
14:15	14:30	Farewell & Perspectives CURAC 2024	
<i>Auditorium U1.131</i>		Georg Rauter	
14:30	16:15	Lab Visit: Department of Biomedical Engineering, University of Basel Georg Rauter (University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland) Hegenheimermattweg 167C, 2nd Floor, 4123 Allschwil Lab: https://biomed.dbe.unibas.ch/ , https://findus.dbe.unibas.ch/	
<i>BIROMED-Lab, DBE</i>			
16:15		End	

Session 1: Robotics and Navigation

A Novel End Effector for Telemanipulated Suturing in Robot-Assisted Laparoscopy

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Suturing is an integral part of surgery. To support this, specialized instruments can be used to facilitate manual needle handling. In particular for suturing tasks, e.g. uterine closure, specialized suturing instruments were designed. In this paper, a novel end effector design integrating an aforementioned conventional suturing instrument is introduced and integrated into the DLR MiroSurge system. The mechanical properties of the end effector are characterized and its basic feasibility for laparoscopic suturing is demonstrated.

Nullspace Control for Automatic Ultrasound Gel Supply

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Ultrasound gel is used as a coupling medium in ultrasound procedures, thereby ensuring the entry of sound waves into the body of the patient and providing ultrasound images of high quality. In this paper, we present an approach to automatically supply ultrasound gel during robot guided ultrasound examinations. For this purpose, we combine a simple mechanical design consisting of a gel tube and a push mechanism with a specialized control strategy exploiting the robotic nullspace of 7 DoF redundant manipulator. Functionality is demonstrated by robotic ultrasound scans on phantoms, with gel being automatically applied when needed.

Robot-assisted Neuroendoscopy: Surgeon's Third Hand – a Proof of Concept Study

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In neuroendoscopy, an assistant surgeon holds the endoscope while the operating surgeon performs brain surgery using surgical instruments in both hands. The assistant surgeon's task can be strenuous over time, especially in long surgeries, and unsteadiness or tremor might affect the visualization quality that the operating surgeon depends upon. Existing mechanical and pneumatic arms offer limited flexibility. We propose a robotic assistant as a third hand to the surgeon. It holds the endoscope and can be moved freely or held in place. As a proof of concept, we attached a neuroendoscope to an off-the-shelf robot with a custom handle, including a force/torque (F/T) sensor. We qualitatively identified the requirements for the third hand with a surgeon as a participant. We also quantitatively identified the range of forces applied by the endoscope to act as a retractor on two brain phantoms while visualizing the surgical site. With our proof of concept study, we could show the feasibility of robotic assistance in neuroendoscopy. Based on our observations, we found that an intuitive input device to switch the different robot modes, a second F/T sensor to measure the surgeon's input and tissue interaction separately, and a differently shaped precision grip handle represent promising improvements to our third hand prototype.

Feasibility and accuracy of CARLO© guided optic canal unroofing

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The primary focus of this study was to assess the feasibility and precision of utilizing CARLO© (Cold Ablation Roboter-guided Laser Osteotome) for marking the boundaries of the optical canal in skull base surgery. The main objective was to accurately delineate the optical canal while minimizing heat damage and preserving vital anatomical structures. The experimental approach involved five fresh frozen skulls, employing preoperative planning through NeuroPlan© and precise bone ablation using a navigation system. Initial findings indicate successful delineating of the optical roof without significant heat damage, underscoring the potential of robotic and laser technologies in improving neurosurgical interventions and enhancing patient outcomes.

Poster Session 1: Short presentation to posters

Spatially-constrained Keypoint Matching for Efficient Statistical Shape Modelling

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Statistical shape models (SSMs) allow the compact description of the variability of object shapes within a given sample set. They are commonly used in medical imaging to model and analyse the shape of anatomical structures such as organs. The generation of a SSM mainly consists of the calculation of the average shape and the main directions of variation of the data set. Usually, structured point clouds are used as shape representations. A crucial step in the calculation of the average shape of the data set represents the transformation of the objects into a common reference space in order to average coordinates of corresponding points. When using unstructured point clouds without explicitly defined landmarks, the matching of correspondences remains a challenge. We propose a novel solution for a spatially-constrained keypoint matching (FPFH++). It is based on a first attempt of a feature-based registration using Fast Point Feature Histograms (FPFH) compared to a baseline approach utilizing Coherent Point Drift (CPD).

Innovating Instrument Handover Techniques for Robotic Scrub Nurses

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A proposed solution to address increasing scarcity of operating room (OR) nurses is the deployment of robotic scrub nurses (RSNs). One of the primary responsibilities of these robots is the handover of surgical instruments to the surgeon. Despite this tasks' apparent simplicity, it requires great precision and timing, while seamless execution is essential for the surgical workflow. This paper outlines the unique challenges of the instrument handover process a RSN and a surgeon that takes place during laparoscopic surgery. After customizing existing solutions from different domains to meet the specific needs of laparoscopic surgery, we introduced these solutions to medical professionals in a simulated OR scenario, and performed a utility analysis to identify the most suitable solutions.

Feasibility and accuracy of CARLO© guided extradural anterior clinoidectomy

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In this study, the feasibility and accuracy of using CARLO© (Cold Ablation Roboter-guided Laser Osteotome) for anterior clinoidectomy were investigated. Anterior clinoidectomy is a challenging and risky neurosurgical procedure due to limited space and proximity to critical anatomical structures. The experiment involved five fresh frozen skulls, and preoperative planning was done using NeuroPlan©. A navigation system and referencing screws ensured precise bone ablation. Initial results suggest successful excavation of the anterior clinoid while preserving critical structures. The study demonstrates the potential of robotic technology in improving neurosurgical procedures and patient outcomes, and may drive further research in this field.

Optical coherence tomography-guided laser osteotomy: toward improvement of ablation efficiency

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This study proposes an additional feature of optical coherence tomography (OCT) as a guidance system for laser surgery, aiming to enhance ablation efficiency during laser osteotomy. A long-range Bessel-like beam OCT system is integrated with an Er:YAG laser. The signal sensitivity of the OCT system is measured under various conditions encountered during laser osteotomy. The results demonstrate that the OCT sensitivity decreases from 87.53 dB to 79.54 dB and 68.93 dB in the presence of debris and water, respectively. These findings highlight the potential application signal sensitivity of OCT as a criterion for detecting the accumulation of water and debris, which could lead to a reduction in ablation efficiency during laser osteotomy using Er:YAG laser.

Feet-Driven 4-Arm Manipulation: A Novel Approach for Solo Laparoscopic Anastomosis

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In laparoscopy, effective collaboration and task performance rely on shared cognition and interaction within human dyadic teams. However, challenges such as miscommunication and increased cognitive workload can arise. Robotic assistants, such as supernumerary robotic manipulators, have emerged as promising solutions to address these issues. This research paper presents a novel approach utilizing feet-driven supernumerary robotic manipulation for solo laparoscopic anastomosis. Two haptic foot interfaces with five degrees of freedom are designed to enable precise and intuitive control by surgeons. Quasi-real-world laparoscopic experiments and subjective evaluations are conducted to assess the system's performance in terms of task workload and usability. Comparative analysis with conventional laparoscopic surgery is also performed. The results of the study (with eleven surgeons familiar with laparoscopy, anastomosis, or both) demonstrated the feasibility of our system in performing laparoscopic tasks, further confirming its potential for enhancing surgical laparoscopic procedures.

Deep Learning-based Artificial Intelligence in Audio based Analysis of Swallowing using Cervical Auscultation

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Structural and/or neurological lesions can cause different forms of swallowing problems, called dysphagia. If substances cannot be safely swallowed into the stomach, they may pass into the lungs and may cause pneumonia, which is associated with high mortality, high morbidity and high cost for the healthcare system. Diagnosis and treatment of dysphagia is important. Diagnostic tests include screening procedures, clinical swallowing examinations, and instrumental examination procedures. Screening procedures do not have good sensitivity with respect to aspiration detection. Technically expensive procedures, such as videofluoroscopy of the swallow (VFSS) - swallowing of contrast agents under x-ray control- and flexible endoscopic evaluation of the swallow (FEES), have the disadvantage of radiation exposure and invasive examination, respectively. As another non-invasive diagnostic option, there is auscultation of the swallowing act. There are different statements about the reliability and validity of the tests. In the present study, fiberendoscopic swallow

examinations were performed simultaneously with cervical auscultation. The evaluation of the swallowing sounds was optimized using artificial intelligence (AI) methods. This allowed the identification of different swallowing patterns in healthy individuals.

Model to Simulate Brain Biopsies Using a Navigated Robotic Guiding System and a Bone Cutting Laser

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This contribution discusses the utilization of a bone cutting laser and a biopsy needle guiding system in brain biopsies to improve their invasiveness, speed, and safety when diagnosing unclear brain lesions. A previous study demonstrated that lasers can create precise burr holes, acting as a guide for the biopsy needle, and enable access to otherwise difficult brain regions. The current research builds on these findings, introducing a biopsy needle attachment for the CARLO© robot, which utilizes an Er:YAG laser and a robotic guiding system.

The study utilizes five frozen skulls, immobilized with a Mayfield clamp, and plans the biopsy path and angle using NeuroPlan© software. Referencing points on the skull and its surface are registered to align the pre-experimental CT scan. A small incision is made to reach the bone area where the laser ablates for the biopsy.

Preliminary results suggest that laser ablation combined with a guidance device allows for precise bone ablation and accurate needle guidance during biopsies. The integration of laser technology and robotics in neurosurgery shows promise for less invasive, faster, and safer biopsies, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Feature Description using Autoencoders for Fast 3D Ultrasound Tracking

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3D ultrasound imaging is a promising modality for therapy guidance, e.g. in radiation therapy. It is able to provide volumetric soft tissue images in real-time. However, due to low image quality, high noise ratio and high data dimensionality, real-time capable US image processing methods like target tracking are challenging. In this study, a feature-based tracking approach is investigated. The FAST feature detector is used to detect local image features in 3D ultrasound images. Two different feature descriptors are tested and evaluated in terms of target tracking: The BRIEF descriptor as well as a slicedwasserstein autoencoder. On the basis of a feature matching algorithm, tracking experiments are executed and evaluated using eight labeled 3D US sequences. The mean tracking error measured is 2.08 ± 1.50 mm and 2.29 ± 1.59 mm using the autoencoder and the BRIEF descriptor, respectively. The results indicate that using an autoencoder for feature description improves the tracking performance compared to a binary descriptor. The proposed tracking method could be executed in fast runtimes of 137 ms and 256 ms per image on average making it real-time capable.

Gamified Virtual Reality Training for Visuospatial Ability in Neuroradiology

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During neuroradiological interventions such as treating intracranial aneurysms, neuroradiologists have to navigate a catheter in the 3D anatomy while watching a 2D projection of the vessels. To train this visuospatial ability, we present a virtual reality application where the user has to identify anatomically relevant positions on the Circle of Willis based on a 2D projection image. This image is generated based on a 3D model using a Fresnel shader. To increase motivation, which is an important aspect in training, we included several game elements. We qualitatively evaluated our application with two

neuroradiologists. Although they rated our implementation of the task as difficult due to the small image section, both participants emphasized the importance of this training. Even small changes that have been suggested can adjust the difficulty, leading to an appropriate training that could be integrated in the curriculum. The results also indicate that the included game elements are motivating and that the application in general has a high usability. The proposed immersive virtual reality application provides a training for visuospatial ability in a concrete medical context. Due to gamification, fun and motivation are increased, which are two important factors of training affecting the frequency of use and outcome.

Target Tracking in 4D Ultrasound using Localization Networks

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In radiation therapy, breathing and other influences cause a constant movement of the tissue to be irradiated. Thus, a continuous position control is required which could be handled by the usage of 3D ultrasound imaging. For this purpose, two approaches for target tracking in 3D ultrasound (US) sequences of the liver are analyzed in this study. Therefore, an image-by-image localization of the target is performed using a deep localization network. A single-target and a multiple-target approach are investigated where deep localization networks are trained for locating one specific and multiple specific targets, respectively. Training the networks and evaluating the tracking algorithm is performed on the basis of a labeled 3D US liver data set in 2-fold cross-validation experiments. The single-target and multiple-target approaches performed comparable with a mean tracking error of 2.28 ± 1.20 mm and 2.23 ± 1.28 mm, respectively. The proposed tracking algorithm is real-time capable with a mean runtime per 3D ultrasound image of 68 ms.

Session 2: Surgical Assistance Systems & Image Processing, Quantification and Visualization

Corrective Cold Ablation Robot-Guided Laser Osteotomies in Wrist Surgery

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The purpose of this study is to show accuracy of a Cold Ablation Robot-Guided Laser Osteotome in pre-clinical cadaver tests, performing osteotomies in the field of wrist- and forearm surgery. Osteotomies were performed with CARLO[®] which is a miniaturized ablation laser with an optical system controlled by a navigation system. A total of 12 corrective laser-osteotomies were performed on the distal metaphyseal radius and ulna. The osteotomies were planned patient specific on a 3D CT-model prior to surgery using CARLO[®]'s planning software. Pre- and postoperative CT-scans were taken to compare the virtual surgical planning with the post-operative results and to show accuracy of the cutting path. First cadaveric results show promising results concerning the accuracy of one and two plane osteotomies in wrist and forearm surgery using a Cold Ablation Robot-Guided Laser Osteotome. Accuracy testing showed that registration of the bone in relation to the patient marker is key to achieve a high precision, therefore it should be done carefully. Future steps are stability testing of the osteosynthesis followed by certification and first use in patients.

Extended upper GI functional assessment in dysphagia by synchronized intraesophageal ultrasound and fluoroscopy

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Functional assessment in dysphagia is mainly based on manometry, pH, impedance and fluoroscopic studies. These diagnostic means each illuminate esophageal (dys)motility from its own side. With the combination of intraesophageal ultrasound it is for the first time possible to assess both the intraluminal bolus transport and the actual resulting muscular response. Especially in complex esophageal motility disorders it is crucial to know the exact pathomechanism of the disease in order to provide patient tailored therapy. The synchronized recordings were analyzed to assess esophageal motility, identification of any structural or functional abnormalities and bolus transit. Preliminary findings indicate that the combination of ultrasound and fluoroscopy provides a comprehensive evaluation in esophageal dysphagia.

Session 3: Best Paper Session

Communication System Using Natural Language for Robotic Laparoscope Guidance

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To help with the critical nurse staffing shortages in hospitals worldwide, robotic assistants are designed to handle frequently required tasks in the digital operating room (DOR), such as the guidance of the laparoscopic camera. To enable fluent collaboration between robots and clinicians, an intuitive and efficient communication interface is needed to allow for interaction using natural language. However, the demanding requirements of the surgical domain make it challenging to develop suitable solutions. A variety of different vocabulary or phrases may be used for expressing the same command. At the same time, surgical workflows may be highly dynamic -- especially in emergency situations -- and thus the system must be able to grasp the user's intent both quickly and with high accuracy. This is especially true as only some clinicians may be authorized to request certain tasks, depending on their rank or field of expertise. To solve these challenges, our proposed communication system uses the fine-tuned deep learning model to recognize the speaker information, and the robot assistant takes action only when it detects the commands from the responsible clinician. Also, our proposed conversational functions enable the fine-tuned large language models to understand the current natural language command given previous command history. In this work, we present a communication system to recognize the speaking person and understand the intent of conversational commands quickly and accurately.

A Laryngoscope with Shape Memory Actuation

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Endotracheal intubation is a medical procedure to secure a patient's airways, which can be challenging in emergency situations due to an individual's anatomy. Intubation blades can benefit from an adjustable design with shape memory alloys. We present a novel blade design with two degrees of freedom, continuously transforming a straight into a curved blade. Our demonstrators reached mean angular deflections up to 16° without exceeding outer blade temperatures of 40 °C. Mean forces of almost 24 N were applicable. This approach has the potential to reduce the complexity of intubation procedures and increase the success rate, especially in time-critical emergency situations.

Characterization of Dynamic Gripping Force Feedback for Robot-Assisted Surgery

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Haptic feedback of gripping forces during robot-assisted surgery can benefit the surgical outcome by means of reduced forces applied to the tissue. A custom-designed haptic user interface allows to control four degrees of freedom of the instrument's endeffector and to display gripping forces. System-centered evaluation is performed to assess its capability of displaying feedback with high mechanical bandwidth. In addition, the perception of gripping forces is evaluated using task-centered methods. Two tasks were performed by ten participants to assess the perceived feedback regarding size and stiffness of grasped objects. Maximum feedback forces of 4.3N and a mechanical bandwidth of 73.5 Hz are achieved. Tests with participants showed promising results regarding the discrimination of size and stiffness of grasped objects.

In situ minimally invasive 3D printing for bone and cartilage regeneration - a scoping review

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Advancements in personalized medicine, three-dimensional (3D) printing, miniaturization, and robot-assisted surgery are driving innovation in tissue engineering. A novel approach, known as in situ printing, focuses on the direct deposition of materials at the surgical site. Using the in situ printing approach, bone and/or cartilage defects can be addressed with high precision. Furthermore, highly customized 3D printed tissue constructs or implants can be deposited directly inside the body. Currently, most applications of in situ printing are limited to areas near the skin or open surgeries. Even though a minimally invasive approach would bring clinical benefits, only a few research groups have focused on this field. In this scoping review, we provide an overview of the current state of in situ minimally invasive three-dimensional printing technology for bone and cartilage regeneration and discuss its advantages and current challenges.

Poster Session 2: Short presentation to posters

6G in Clinical Applications: Integrating New Network Approaches in Healthcare

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The increase in staff shortage, particularly in urgently needed care professions, is becoming an immense problem in the German healthcare system. This critical issue is further intensified by the fact that the healthcare system is still a strongly human-dependent and often insufficiently interconnected environment. Automation, medical robotics and the concept of model-based medicine can play a key role not only in addressing these issues and supporting clinical staff, but also in enabling new applications to improve patient care. While many existing approaches aim to tackle these challenges, they are generally based on current network architectures and standards and are thus constrained by the limitations of these networks. This article highlights the need for new network approaches to provide flexible, dynamic structures, new communication classes and many other new features in order to leverage the true potential of these new technologies.

Speech Recognition for the Sterile Interaction with Information Systems in the Surgical Area

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This paper describes how automatic speech recognition (ASR) can be used to explore electronic patient records (EPR) in a sterile environment. As an information display, we used a system that was developed for the presentation of patient data and for supporting surgical hand disinfection. The speech recognition was performed using the Mozilla Web Speech API. A room microphone, a Jabra Box, and a directional microphone, a RØDE NT-USB Mini, were tested at various positions. Interactions with the EPR are triggered with a list of commands. The interaction was working as intended and test persons reported the system as intuitive.

Center for Intelligent Optics

F. Canbaz

University of Basel, Switzerland

The center for intelligent optics focuses on the development of intelligent optical technologies that can be used in treatment, diagnosis, and imaging for basic research and clinical applications. The goal is also to miniaturize these optical systems for minimally invasive surgery applications. Depending on the application, we use the existing or home-built systems to develop new technologies. Using these systems on such a complicated system as the human body also requires utilizing machine learning algorithms.

Session 4: Intelligent OR Technique & Machine Learning

Towards examiner-independent reproducible abdominal ultrasound examinations

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The proposed system aims at reproducibility in ultrasound follow-up examinations by storing the position of the ultrasound transducer in relation to acquired images. The system utilizes an electromagnetic tracking system. It includes a guidance feature to assist in placing the transducer correctly on the patient. Evaluation of the system involved technical accuracy tests on a phantom and accuracy tests on human subjects. The results showed that the technical accuracy of the system met the required criteria, but the transducer positioning error in realistic scenarios was above the threshold. Usability testing indicated potential benefits for medical training and provided suggestions for improving the user interface. Overall, the system shows promise for further development and can already be used for training ultrasound examinations.

Dynamic Torque Limitation vs Static Torque Limitation for Bone Screws in Pig Bone.

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Correctly torquing bone screws is important to achieve good patient outcomes. An automated system has been previously proposed that may allow more objective torquing of bone screws. Here the system is tested vs a static torque limit in pig bone. 5 screws were first inserted until stripping to calibrate the dynamic and static limits. Then 6 were inserted limited to 80% of the mean stripping torque. Then 7 were inserted using 80% of the dynamic model-predicted stripping torque. The pull-out strength of the dynamic and static insertions were compared and no statistically significant difference was found. Future work should consider at using larger screws and different bone samples, with more repetitions to try and obtain a statistically significant result.

Contactless Energy Supply for Medical Drill with integrated Temperature Sensor

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The current surgical process for electrode insertion for cochlear implantations is highly invasive. To reduce invasiveness minimally invasive surgery options are researched, e.g. the insertion of one or more drilling channels. Due to the vicinity to critical structures, a temperature sensor is included in the medical drill for process parallel temperature surveillance to prevent thermal damage. The temperature data collected with the drill is sent to a processing hardware through Bluetooth BLE. Thus, energy supply to the electronic on the drill is necessary. For the development of such an energy supply some restrictions have to be taken into account. For one, the drill is rotating. Therefore, the energy generation has to be contactless. Secondly, it should be possible to measure the temperature even without the drill spinning. The energy generation should therefore not depend on the rotation of the drill. In this paper, we propose a solution for a contactless energy transmission system based on inductive coupling. Considering the dimensional restrictions of attaching the electronic to the drill shaft, a multilayer PCB coil with multiple contacts for a different number of turns is developed. The electric circuit is simulated and the best settings are

identified. The energy supply is finally validated according to the pre-defined requirements. In the future, the medical drill with the newly developed energy transmission system will be built. Sterilization and wear tests will be carried out to confirm the suitability of the drill with integrated temperature sensor for the operating room.

Adaptive Contrast Enhancement for Digital Radiographic Images using Image-to-Image Translation

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Digital radiography in medicine is a widely used imaging method for obtaining visual information about the inside of a body. To prepare the acquired raw image for diagnostic evaluation, the contrast must be adjusted depending on the examined part of the body and the reason of acquisition. The contrast enhancement of an image can be considered as a style transfer or an image-to-image translation which is an important field in deep learning. Based on common methods like the pix2pix network that only translate from one domain into one other, we propose a method (cc-pix2pix) for translating into multiple domains in one training. We provide additional information about the examination to the network for a specific contrast adjustment. Compared to the pix2pix network, the cc-pix2pix reduces the mean squared error by a factor of six and achieves an improvement of approximately seven percentage points based on the histogram intersection of source and target images.

Session 5: Modeling and Simulation

Morphologic and hemodynamic analysis of intracranial mirror aneurysms

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Intracranial mirror aneurysms are pathologic dilatations of cerebral arteries that occur at identical locations in both hemispheres. They do not always have identical sizes, shapes, or rupture states, despite identical patient-specific risk factors. As a subgroup of multiple aneurysms and thus small amounts of data, clinical research about their causes and development has not been conclusive. Using eight patients with 16 mirror aneurysms with different rupture states, we investigated differences between the hemispheres. We virtually performed stitching: detaching the aneurysm domes to place them on the opposite parent vessel to assess influence of aneurysm morphology and upstream parent vessel shape on hemodynamics. In the unaltered datasets, we found that the left hemisphere has higher wall shear stress and velocity before stitching. After stitching, we found that both upstream parent vessel as well as aneurysm morphology have an influence on hemodynamics, though morphologic parameters like size and undulation index, as well as aneurysm angle had a higher influence. In a short rupture risk analysis we found a correlation between rupture and aspect ratio and non-sphericity index. Overall, we found possible indicators for mirror aneurysm analysis, though for conclusive statements more datasets are necessary.

Testing of Bone-Implant Systems equipped with a Fracture Monitor regarding Interfragmentary Movement – A Simulation-Based Workflow

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Introduction: Fractures of the lower extremity are common and have been experiencing an increasing incidence. An important factor that significantly influences the dynamics of the healing process is the activity level of the patient and the associated load on the fractured limb.

Methods: The aim of this study is an experimental investigation of fracture gap displacement using a testing device which replicates the loading scenarios during a gait cycle on human tibia from body donations in combination with finite element simulation, along with the utilization of the new Fracture Monitor developed by AO Foundation, to correlate the surface strain of the implant with the corresponding load.

Results: It has been successfully demonstrated that the results of Fracture Monitor correlate highly with the surface strain of the implant as measured by digital image correlation. Furthermore, these findings have been corroborated by finite element simulations based on various knee joint forces. Additionally, the experimental analysis allows the evaluation of interfragmentary movement of the fracture gap during the experimental procedure.

Conclusion: Widen the knowledge of the interfragmentary movement and bone-implant behaviour is important to understand the healing process and the local micro-mechanic inside the fracture gap.

Hyper-redundant endoscopic manipulator position compensation under external load

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This paper focuses on determining the cable tensions required for a cable-driven endoscopic manipulator to compensate for an external load and return to its initial position. A simulation was performed using MATLAB, where mathematical models and algorithms were used to calculate the required tension. The mathematical model, based on Optimized Motion Estimation Analysis, considers the joint stiffness and the influence of gravity, in addition to the cable tensions and external load. The algorithm minimizes the sum of moments to achieve a stable and balanced position. The simulation results were validated against the experimental data. The manipulator successfully compensated for an external load of 1.96 N and returned to its initial position with adjusted cable tensions. The results showed that the manipulator was deformed by an external load, highlighting the need to adjust the cable tension for position compensation. The discrepancies between the experimental and simulation results were due to factors such as marker size and positioning uncertainty, as well as joint imperfections and friction effects. Nevertheless, the proposed method proved to be effective in compensating for external loads and restoring the manipulator to the desired position.

Interactive Surgical Liver Phantom for Cholecystectomy Training

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Training and prototype development in robot-assisted surgery requires appropriate and safe environments for the execution of surgical procedures. Current dry lab laparoscopy phantoms often lack the ability to mimic complex, interactive surgical tasks. This work presents an interactive surgical phantom for the cholecystectomy. The phantom enables the removal of the gallbladder during cholecystectomy by allowing manipulations and cutting interactions with the synthetic tissue. The force-displacement behavior of the gallbladder is modelled based on retraction demonstrations. The force model is compared to the force model of ex-vivo porcine gallbladders and evaluated on its ability to estimate retraction forces.

A Calibration Approach for Elasticity Estimation with Medical Tools

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Soft tissue elasticity is directly related to different stages of diseases and can be used for tissue identification during minimally invasive procedures. By palpating a tissue with a robot in a minimally invasive fashion force-displacement curves can be acquired. However, force-displacement curves strongly depend on the tool geometry which is often complex in the case of medical tools. Hence, a tool calibration procedure is desired to directly map force-displacement curves to the corresponding tissue elasticity. We present an experimental setup for calibrating medical tools with a robot. First, we propose to estimate the elasticity of gelatin phantoms by spherical indentation with a state-of-the-art contact model. We estimate force-displacement curves for different gelatin elasticities and temperatures. Our experiments demonstrate that gelatin elasticity is highly dependent on temperature, which can lead to an elasticity offset if not considered. Second, we propose to use a more complex material model, e.g., a neural network, that can be trained with the determined elasticities. Considering the temperature of the gelatin sample we can represent different elasticities

per phantom and thereby increase our training data. We report elasticity values ranging from 10 to 40 kPa for a 10% gelatin phantom, depending on temperature.

Symmetric single-input eccentric tube robot (ETR) for manual use

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Concentric tube robots (CTR) have gained popularity in robotic research due to their potential for smaller instrument sizes, enhanced dexterity and reduced trauma. However, CTR modeling and path-planning can be complex. To address this, a symmetric eccentric tube robot (ETR) setup is presented, where three identical pre-curved wires are arranged in parallel and constrained by an outer sheath. Curvature is controlled by a single input angle. This study aims to demonstrate the suitability as manually actuated instrument. A model for curvature as a function of input angle is presented, and a prototype ETR with an outer diameter of 1~mm is assembled and evaluated. The results show that the ETR follows the expected shape, the curvature decreasing with the separation angle in a way that may be perceived as intuitive and predictable by the human user. However, some unsteady behavior (snapping) is observed, which may be addressed by preventing torsion through mechanical means. The simplified model neglecting the sheath stiffness provides precise enough predictions for the working space of a manual ETR. The findings suggest that manual ETRs have potential applications in superficial interventions, such as injections, arthroscopy, or ophthalmic surgery, where their curved section can be beneficial in comparison to current straight needles. Further research could explore interlocking mechanical designs to prevent torsion and enable modular setups for enhanced functionality in surgical procedures.

Session 6: Image Processing, Quantification and Visualization

Pose Measurement of the EndoWrist Round Tip Scissor Instrument with Optical Coherence Tomography

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To automate surgical (sub-)tasks in robotic surgery, the knowledge of the exact pose of the instrument is mandatory. The application of Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) to the problem of pose measurement appears promising due to its advantages of 3D imaging and micron-scale resolution. To investigate this, 175 image sequences of the EndoWrist Round Tip Scissor Tool were acquired with an OCT system. The images differ in the opening angles of the scissor blades and the rotation angles of the entire instrument about its central axis. These image sequences were further processed through computer vision methods of the individual images followed by point cloud generation. For pose estimation, an Iterative Closest Point algorithm was implemented to register the acquired point clouds to reference point clouds created from the instrument CAD file. The implemented algorithm was able to determine the opening angle with an overall error of $2^\circ \pm 1.3^\circ$ and the rotation angle with a standard deviation between several runs of $0.6^\circ \pm 2.8^\circ$ and is therefore well suited for this task. However, the overall processing time of (39±17)s on a standard PC leaves room for further investigations.

Correlating Cerebral Aneurysm Size Measurements Based On Virtual Reality Versus Standard 2D DSA Measurements; A Randomized Comparative Study

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Aims

Size diameters are a critical factor in determining rupture risk for unruptured intracranial aneurysms (UIA). Virtual-reality (VR) models provide 3D visualization, potentially enhancing the accuracy of measurements. This study aims to correlate measurements in 3D VR with source 2D images assessing the accuracy of 3D VR as a measurement tool.

Methods

Ten UIA-case Images were converted into a 3D VR model using "SpectoVR." A patient-specific transfer function was applied to segment bone and vessels. Five neurosurgeons were randomly assigned to the cases. Each performed measurements in 3D VR and 2D on-screen format. Interrater variability, measurement duration, and VR user experience were assessed.

Results

Measurements of anteroposterior (3D VR 5.65 ± 5 vs. 2D 5.64 ± 5 , $p=0.652$), mediolateral (5.44 ± 3.7 vs. 5.70 ± 5.1 , $p=0.703$), craniocaudal (5.81 ± 5 vs. 6.19 ± 4.6 , $p=0.219$) showed significant correlations between 3D VR and 2D. No significant differences in interrater variability were observed. Measurement duration did not vary significantly (8.31 ± 15 min vs. 7.1 ± 11 min, $p=0.118$). All investigators found 3D VR models more intuitive and desired increased utilization.

Conclusion

3D VR technology provides significantly correlated basic measurements to 2D images. It improves accuracy for non-axial sizes such as parent artery and neck diameters due to its enhanced precision without significantly increasing measurement duration.

VR-based body tracking to stimulate musculoskeletal training

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Training helps to maintain and improve sufficient muscle function, body control, and body coordination. These are important to reduce the risk of fracture incidents caused by falls, especially for the elderly or people recovering from injury. Virtual reality training can offer a cost-effective and individualized training experience.

We present an application for the HoloLens 2 to enable musculoskeletal training for elderly and impaired persons to allow for autonomous training and automatic progress evaluation. We designed a virtual downhill skiing scenario that is controlled by body movement to stimulate balance and body control. By adapting the parameters of the ski slope, we can tailor the intensity of the training to the individual user. In this work, we evaluate whether the movement data of the HoloLens 2 alone is sufficient to control and predict body movement and joint angles during musculoskeletal training.

We record the movements of 10 healthy volunteers with external tracking cameras and track a set of body and joint angles of the participant during training. We estimate correlation coefficients and systematically analyze whether whole body movement can be derived from the movement data of the HoloLens 2. No participant reports movement sickness effects and all were able to quickly interact and control their movement during skiing. Our results show a high correlation between HoloLens 2 movement data and the external tracking of the upper body movement and joint angles of the lower limbs.

Intraoperative navigated ultrasound in posterior fossa surgery

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Especially in the semi-sitting position navigation accuracy might be limited. Intraoperative ultrasound (iUS) imaging therefore might serve as valuable tool to intraoperatively quantify navigation accuracy or in case update navigation by the acquisition of iUS data sets. Data of 23 patients (28 lesions) undergoing navigation supported surgery in the posterior fossa with application of iUS were evaluated. In nine cases (eleven lesions) navigation was rated "insufficient" leading to a navigation update by manually outlining the tumor volumes within the iUS data set, whereas in all other cases navigation accuracy was rated "sufficient" with no need for further updates. IUS was successful implemented in navigation supported surgery within the posterior fossa and allowed for evaluation of navigation accuracy and even navigation updates, supporting safe maximum tumor resection.